

D6.3

Communication & Dissemination plan and visual identity handbook

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ALICE	Alliance For Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe
API	Application Programming Interface
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ERTICO	European Road Transport Implementation Co-Ordination
HR	Human Resources
ITV	Technical Vehicle Inspection
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NAPCORE	National Access Point Coordination Organization for Europe
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
R&D	Research & Development
REACH	Rational Environment Addressed Clear Holistic
SC	Steering Committee
TRA	Transport Research Arena
TUV	Technical Inspection Association
UKRI	United Kingdom's Research & Innovation
VIH	Visual Identity Handbook
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

Within the scope of the KEYSTONE project, Work Package (WP) 6 – Communication, Dissemination, Replicability and Exploitation, Deliverable D6.3 intends to provide a detailed communication and dissemination plan, containing the methodology to be followed, the planned activities for all partners to ensure the widest possible outreach and collaboration with project results and findings for the duration of the project, which has started on 01 June 2023 and lasts until 21 May 2026.

Additionally, the report includes the Visual Identity Handbook (VIH), presenting the final project logo, the branding guidelines, the final templates for the written report, and in addition PowerPoint presentations that will be used by all partners during the project to ensure a harmonised and clear branding of the project across dissemination activities, channels and languages.

The aim of the Communication Plan is to set the basis for a successful and effective communication and dissemination plan and identify and raise awareness among the targeted audience. The main Project activities covered by this deliverable are:

1. Communication and dissemination tools, plan and methodology;
2. KEYSTONE project targeted audience;
3. An editorial plan specifying the activities to be followed within the upcoming three years of the duration of the project;
4. Definition of KPIs and a strategic plan to ensure the success of the activities.

Meanwhile, the VIH provides a detailed guide and the final templates that will be used for all internal and external communication activities throughout the project, to ensure the recognition of KEYSTONE in workshops, events, publications, and other dissemination actions. The written and visual identity of the project is essential to support all dissemination activities.

The VIH presents the visual image of KEYSTONE, namely the project logo, which is to be used throughout the duration of the project to ensure a recognisable visual image for all communication activities. This document will be a reference point for the upcoming communication and dissemination activities that will be implemented throughout the duration of the KEYSTONE project so that all partners are informed about the activities to be followed. It can also be considered a living document, as some of its parts may be revised and modified along the project duration, depending on external circumstances, market research and the successfulness of the different actions. The main goal is to reach the target audiences in the best and most direct way possible and ensure that clear messages reach their attention in due time.

2. Communication & Dissemination Plan

KEYSTONE (Knowledgeable Comprehensive and fully integrated Smart solutions for resilient, sustainable, and optimized transport operations) is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), funded under the Horizon Europe framework program of the European Commission (EC) under Grant Agreement Number 101103740 and under the United Kingdom's Research & Innovation (UKRI) fund under Horizon Europe.

All the communication and dissemination activities of the KEYSTONE project and their outcomes will guarantee that the stakeholders are reached and involved in the achievement of KEYSTONE's objectives. The communication and dissemination strategy should focus heavily on the key stakeholders of the logistics and compliance sector and aim at not only informing them but also involving them interactively into the project activities and communications.

This document represents the key reference document for all consortium partners as the project progresses and communication & dissemination activities intensify.

2.1 Objectives and Methodology

There is a lack of any universal EU-wide API standard for the secure exchange, transfer, and sharing of sensitive documentation between operators crossing the EU borders and the enforcement authorities. The concept of the development and conceptualization of a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport system that allows operators and authorities to exchange data for compliance checks in a secure, simple, and fast-track way has not been achieved yet. The goals of KEYSTONE are:

- Providing standardized fast-track digital solutions to the transport system;
- Demonstrating the competence of the project through a comprehensive web app solution via two highly diverse pilots;
- Developing a faultless digital transport ecosystem;
- Identifying API standards for data and information sharing between operators and authorities;
- Contributing to the reduction of costs and CO2 footprint and endorsing the acceptance of CCAM technologies solutions in the future;
- Promoting the engagement of stakeholders through various channels (media, social media) and enhance their participation in all communication activities;
- Increasing the engagement of the targeted groups through different events (webinars, beta testing, agora sessions, etc.).

In an attempt to achieve the above, KEYSTONE hereby produces a set of guidelines to ensure engagement with the audience and meanwhile the creation of awareness to the public: the communication and dissemination strategy of the project follows the REACH methodology (**R**ational means; **E**nabling environment, capacity, and ownership; **A**ddressed communication and awareness; **C**lear strategic planning; **H**olistic approach). These principles are applied to all of the planned communication and dissemination activities of the project from the very beginning.

KEYSTONE seeks to be a landmark project, leaving a notable impact on both the industry and authorities affected by the project and gather a large following to push forward the uptake of the KEYSTONE solution and influence policy making and standardization processes much beyond the project duration.

It is important to differentiate clearly between the terminology of communication and dissemination. While the former has a more general objective and should be addressed to larger groups such as the general public to promote the project or its results, the later seeks in sending a clear message, outcome or research finding to a group of experts who are interested in reviewing, further developing or adopting the results of the project.

Ideally, KEYSTONE activities should consist of both, with a focus on dissemination to relevant stakeholder groups due to the TRL of the solution and the high context for professional use and applications.

Figure 1 - Differentiation of communication and dissemination activities (European Commission, 2021)

Finally, a set of 5 basic principles are applied to the entirety of the project, including the communication and dissemination activities, but also all other activities to ensure that the project findings don't only reach the widest possible audience, but also that the information is always presented in an accessible way depending on the target audience and purpose of the activity:

Table 1 - KEYSTONE Communication and dissemination principles

Principle	Activities
User-Orientation	Different target groups are targeted and defined for every communication & dissemination activity to ensure any recipient only receives relevant information and to pre-filter information for the convenience of the stakeholder.
Open	KEYSTONE vouches to openly incorporate external ideas into its dissemination activities. This includes establishing links with other European initiatives and stakeholders and sharing any insights or learnings freely, by rendering them accessible to anyone.
Comprehensive	The declared target of KEYSTONE is to address all types of logistics stakeholders as well as the enforcement authorities and the general public as a whole. Each deliverable should contain enough information to allow insights to be exploited directly by anyone and offers all learnings as well as their implications at once.
Adapted	A "smart approach" takes into consideration the specific interests and existing knowledge base of different target groups and to adapt the messages and communication channels accordingly. This ensures that anyone, no matter their familiarity with the topics at hand can easily comprehend and use the project results.

Global	Although the key target of SALIENT are European logistics stakeholder, a global outreach is desirable and can be achieved by exchanging with non-European initiatives and organisations. This can also help in exporting important insights to economically less-favoured world areas.
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Based on these principles, almost all information stemming from the communication and the dissemination of project results consists of encultured knowledge, which means that it contains novel insights while representing a collective endeavour from an organisational point of view. In light of this, all activity should also align with one of two different strategies, which have been identified as appropriate for the KEYSTONE Project (Tidd & Bessant, 2009):

1. Integration for the implementation of functional knowledge acquired during the course of this project;
2. Transfer through exploiting existing knowledge in a new context.

Furthermore, considering a process model of knowledge management for innovation, it is subsequently possible to identify some concrete guidelines, which are relevant for the project and need to be kept in mind during the design and execution of communication and dissemination activities (Tranfield, Young, Partington, & Bessant, 2006):

Figure 2 - Knowledge management

Finally, since all activities take place in countries with different languages, all content is available in English first, while some dissemination materials could also eventually be translated into the local languages of the consortium (namely Estonian, French, German, Greek, Italian and Spanish) if required.

2.1.1 Key Performance Indicators

The success of the communication and dissemination plan for the SCALE-UP project can be evaluated by using the Table 2 below, where KPIs are listed. The KPIs are continuously reported upon by all partners, using a simple Google Form in a survey layout to quickly gather and quantify each and every dissemination action along the project. The KPIs are reported upon in the bi-monthly WP6 meetings. Depending on the responses, possible risks can be flagged early enough and adequate mitigation actions can be devised amongst the consortium partners. In case there is any deviation from the initial plan, this shall be reported in

the final report, submitted at the end of the project, and additionally during the annual project events in form of a more detailed annual review and adjacent workshop.

Table 2 - KEYSTONE Communication & dissemination KPIs

KEYSTONE Communication & Dissemination KPIs		Period		
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Website	Visits/ month	200	250	350
	Individual visitors	100	150	200
	Blog posts/ month	1	1	1
e-Newsletters	Editions/ year	3	4	4
	Subscribers	80	100	120
Video Clips	Editions	-	1	2
Social Media	Posts/ year	24	36	48
	Posts/ month	2	2	2
	Followers (cross- platform)	100	150	200
Media	Coverages	5	10	20
Printed Materials	Roll-ups	1	-	1
	Posters	1	2	2
	Brochures	-	1	1
	Total distributed (all materials)	100	200	300
Publications	Conference Papers	-	3	3
	Journal Papers	-	2	2
Events	Project Events	1	1	1
	Attendance to external events	3	5	6

While these KPIs have been planned and approved by all consortium partners, it is clear that their distribution over the years is an estimated editorial plan. A copy of the above Table 2 has been created and is reported on during the bi-monthly meetings to gather an oversight over the progress and success of the different dissemination activities by all partners.

2.1.2 Target Audience Groups

To ensure the success of the communication strategy the target audience groups need to be defined. The target audience of the communication and dissemination strategy for the KEYSTONE project has been defined as five stakeholder groups that are listed below in Table 3. However, the target audience is not limited only to those who will benefit from the outcomes of the project. There is a wide range of targeted groups at the national, European, and international level who is relevant to the project's activities and can benefit from its outcome.

Furthermore, it is important to keep in mind that during communication activities, also the general public and any other target group may be taken into the focus. In general, KEYSTONE dissemination seeks to always prepare materials and contents, which are multi-dimensional by containing descriptive elements for audiences outside the logistics sector and highlight technical or professional highlights for audience members with a higher understanding and experience of the subjects. This ensures that persons less familiar with the subject are informed of its importance and key objective, while professionals or academics can understand the specific advantage and cutting edge of KEYSTONE at the same time. More detailed (technical) information will be made available in a second layer for those who seek this information background and/or citation of sources.

Table 3 - KEYSTONE Communication target audience groups

Target Groups	Stakeholders	Communication Action
Enforcement Authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional, national, and border police. Traffic police authorities. Military services Frontex services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual Project Events Conference Papers Journal Papers
Logistics Companies & Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Owners and staff of logistics companies (mid-sized until multi-national companies); Operators (drivers or operations team); Training authorities for drivers in a professional level; Supply Chain stakeholders; HR personnel; NGOs; Any other platform representing interests and rights in the EU. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social Media Accounts E-newsletter Project Website Project Videoclip Project Roll-up & Posters Project Brochures Annual Project Events Attendance to external events
Research Centres	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research centres (both focusing on logistics and transport R&D); R&D departments of commercial companies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E-newsletter Project Website Project Brochures Conference Papers Journal Papers Annual Project Events
Local Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small scale logistics companies; Companies working closely with logistics; Customers of the logistics operators; Local technical checkpoints; Training centres for professional drivers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social Media Accounts E-newsletter Project website Project Videoclip Project Roll-Up & Posters Conference Papers Journal Papers Annual Project Events
National & Regional Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automobile clubs; Public authorities (councils, parliaments, ministries); Certification bodies (TÜV, ITV, etc.) ; Training centres for handling of dangerous goods. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual Project Events Attendance to external events Conference Papers
European Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Platforms on logistics & transport (such as ALICE, ERTICO, EU parliament, EU authorities and NGOs); Standardisation bodies (CEN). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E-newsletter Conference Papers Journal Papers Annual Project Events Attendance to external Events
Press & Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Journalistic news outlets; Media channels specialised for professionals; National or regional news. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social Media Accounts E-newsletter Project website Annual Project Events
Industry Operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacturers of equipment; Service Providers for logistics company; Planning Authorities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social Media Accounts Dedicated e-newsletter Project Website Project Videoclip

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Roll-up & Posters • Project Brochures • Annual Project Events
Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University Departments and their staff (focusing on logistics and transport); • Higher education bodies; • University consortia and alliances. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • e-newsletter • Project Website • Project Brochures • Conference Papers • Journal Papers • Annual Project Events
Related R&D Initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any other related project under the same call; • Other global research consortia on related topics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project Website • Conference Papers • Journal Papers • Annual Project Events

2.2 KEYSTONE Digital Communication Tools

Several digital communication channels have been created to inform and regularly update the targeted groups and the public on the latest KEYSTONE news and activities. These tools have a high impact on the success of the dissemination strategy, as digital tools permit an increasing targeting of individuals, user groups and professionals and therefore allow the consortium to truly penetrate the target audience groups directly with clear messages via advertising, targeting, campaigning and advanced analytics. All of the tools and target areas detailed below are therefore of high relevance and impact to the communication & dissemination strategy of the project, especially since many of everyday professional and personal interactions have moved online during and as an aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. Detailing a good digital communication strategy is the carrying pillar of any successful company, initiative or project in the 2020’s. Out of many possible goals of a communication strategy, KEYSTONE will focus on 2 driving aims (Meerman Scott, 2009):

1. Building a brand: creating a branding for KEYSTONE to enhance the legacy potential and replication of the project for a landmark project and commercial uptake;
2. Generating awareness: casting a wide net to inform future adopters of the outcomes for exploitation beyond the duration of the funded project.

2.2.1 Website

The KEYSTONE official website (www.keystone-project.com) is a virtual communication and dissemination vehicle, informing the public about the latest news and activities. The website consists of well-designed images and graphics aiming to demonstrate the main goal of the project and guides the visitor intuitively through the different aspects of the website. Photos of the design and content of the website are provided, in ANNEX I - Website Overview a website’s overview can be found. Similar to the distribution of KPIs, the website is a living information platform, which is adapted depending on the stage of the project. For example, during the first 6 months of the project, users will be able to access the stakeholder consultation survey of T1.1, while in later stages they are guided to download the web app once it is completed to perform UI/UX testing on it within the WP3 activities to provide feedback. Each page contains at the bottom the obligatory funding and copyright disclaimer of the Horizon Europe programme and links to the detailed privacy policy of the website. Furthermore, a cookie policy has been devised and an automated disclaimer has been activated and a form to subscribe to the “KEYSTONE In Action” newsletter has been added to the bottom of all pages to ensure easy findability of the form and push users to subscribe to the newsletter. Some 7 pages are going to be carried across the entire project, as they are pivotal to document and give any visitor all of the general basic information they might seek about the project, namely:

1. **Homepage:** The homepage welcomes the visitor with a catchy motto and pushes the user to access the sub-section on the web app (one of the main KERs) by design, while also providing them with

links to other sub-pages such as an overview of the consortium partners or the resources section. It also links directly to the twitter activities of the project and shows the latest pieces of news at a glance.

2. **About:** The “About” section contains information about the main objectives, the overall duration of the project, and how the audience (targeted & and general) can engage in the activities of the project are presented.
3. **Partners:** In the “Partners” section, a presentation of the consortium is provided, which consists of 15 partners from six countries across the continent, including an interactive map and partner profiles, which contain all partners logos and link to their websites. Eventually, this section may be expanded to present each partner’s organization in greater detail on dedicated sub-pages and/or even introduce the team members of each organization so that visitors can identify the consortium member they’d like to get in contact with directly.
4. **App:** In the “App” section, the visitor can find detailed information about the development and implementation of a comprehensive web app, one of the main objectives of the KEYSTONE project. This page is designed in an almost commercial manner with modern illustrations and graphics and can eventually contain a form to register for beta-testing activities and/or pilot the solution on additional pilots. It will also contain mock-ups and demos of the application once it has been fully conceptualized within WP2 and developed within WP3.
5. **Updates:** The latest news, updates, and information about the latest activities concerning the project are featured in the “News” section in a blog-style to keep the audience informed about the recent and upcoming activities, and to raise awareness. The news may be filtered according to years, so that visitors are able to access all information easily. Furthermore, a sub-section has been added containing all newsletter editions that have been published in an archive.
6. **Resources:** One section is dedicated to the project resources, where visitor can find all the approved deliverables, recordings of events and webinars and other publications (such as conference or scientific papers or public datasets from surveys and consultation activities). Here, they can also receive an overview of the reporting process and all the dissemination materials, both online and offline, and the visual identity of KEYSTONE.
7. **Contact:** The page “Contact” provides a contact email address, for every person that would like to share feedback, ideas, or any other information relevant to the project.
8. **Privacy policy, Cookie policy and GDPR compliance:** At the borderline of every section of the website, the disclaimer can be found, providing information about the funding of the project from the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme, specifying the number of the Grant Agreement, and the co-funding by the European Union. The European flag and the funding statement are also demonstrated, in a distinct and separate section. Additionally, the logo of the UK Research and Innovation is presented. Additionally, a privacy policy statement is provided in all webpages, highlighting the data collection process and providing additional information about the data treatment and detailing what kind of information is collected, how it is processed and stored and why it is GDPR compliant. The cookies policy is activated on the website, a pop-up window is informing the visitor about this policy when visiting the webpage.
9. **Social Media:** Two links with quick access to the social media channels of the project (Twitter/X and LinkedIn) are provided on every webpage, to promote the engagement of the audience in the social media channels.

2.2.1.1 News Articles

As a basis for all digital communication and dissemination activities, news articles are drafted by the consortium partners and the dissemination leader STA. Each news article is posted on the KEYSTONE website and receives a unique URL slug and tracking to measure the traffic it generates on the website and to measure the popularity and success of different topics and visuals. Documenting the progress and results of the project has some key advantages:

1. Via the website settings, a visual can be defined which will be attached to the URL wherever it is shared (a so-called “social image”), which presents the link in a more appealing visual way when shared on social media or across messenger services directly. Since the image will be the same for all platforms or messages, it creates a recognisability of the content;
2. All news and updates are documented in an organised archive on the website and can be accessed via open access by anyone at any time, documenting for partners inside and outside the consortium the progress and activities of the project;
3. Pieces of news can easily be integrated into the quarterly newsletter, since they are in blog format and can be exported into the newsletter service directly.

Pieces of news are discussed bi-monthly during the KEYSTONE WP6 meetings, where ideas for new articles are exchanged and it is clearly defined who will author and who will peer-review the news article before it is posted to the website. A backlog of minimum 4 news articles should be kept to schedule their publication and integration into the newsletter editions accordingly and also to ensure that neither the KEYSTONE website nor its social media channels are “abandoned” during holiday or vacation seasons when the consortium partners might be less active (e.g., late December, July/August).

Accounting for seasonal availabilities and peak work sprints in the preparation of deliverables allows the consortium to take a strategic approach to communication and dissemination and carefully define the best possible moment to share specific information or results with target groups during key moments of the project.

Since the beginning of the project’s implementation, four pieces of news have already been published:

1. KEYSTONE project kicks off (20/06/2023);
2. Consortium gets together (22/06/2023);
3. KEYSTONE project calls for participation (27/07/2023);
4. Stakeholder community survey launched (15/09/2023).

Seven more have already been titled, scheduled and attributed a lead author:

1. An article focusing on stakeholders' needs and requirements and stating how they can benefit from KEYSTONE (T1.1., University of Coventry, December 2023);
2. The development of the web app solution and the API reference model, as well as the implementation of the Plug and Play Framework (T2.1, Aethon Engineering, December 2023);
3. The use cases from the perspective of the enforcement authorities, explain their needs and obstacles (Corte, October 2023);
4. The use cases presented by the logistics operators' perspective highlight their needs and what can be improved (Gruber & CIM, October 2023);
5. The dissemination materials launching will be presented in an article introducing all the materials of the project (STA, November 2023);
6. Article in the Agenda Digitale magazine (English translation) (Cefriel & STA, September 2023).
7. Press release on “Logisticamente.it” (Cefriel, October 2023).

2.2.2 Newsletter

The KEYSTONE newsletter, named “KEYSTONE In Action”, is published quarterly informing the audience about the latest news, updates, and about former and upcoming activities. The newsletter consists of six pieces of news, three news related to the KEYSTONE project, and three external news. It highlights the latest results, the activities related to the project, and other relevant information to inform the subscribers about the project’s progress. The newsletter is sent every three months to the registered audience, that has been

subscribed to the mailing list with their email address. It will be published and shared with all the subscribers of the mailing list.

The aim is to increase the number of subscribers during year 1 and year 2 of KEYSTONE. For this reason, all consortium partners are encouraged to promote the subscription to colleagues and people related to the fields of the project to achieve the KPIs. Only within the first 3 months of the project, 51 individuals subscribed to the newsletter and it can be expected that this growth trend continues as the news and message of KEYSTONE are shared by all consortium partners.

The newsletter can also be used to publish and amplify the impact of calls for contributions, such as the announcement for stakeholders to take part in survey, focus discussion groups, webinars, trainings, events and other activities organized under the project.

Included in the newsletter registration form on the website is a disclaimer, which states that by registering, users consent to the website's privacy policy and in parallel consent to be contacted for consultation and co-creation activities of the project in case that they qualify to become a member of the stakeholder community.

2.2.3 Social Media Channels

Two social media channels were launched (Twitter/X & LinkedIn) at the beginning of the project to engage the targeted audience and achieve recognition by the wide public and should be checked every day to ensure the following up with the audience and not to miss any important communication. A new post should be published bi-weekly, and a new piece of news should be shared monthly, to ensure a constant and relevant production of content for the audience. The partners are informed of the need to promote the social media channels and highly participate by regularly posting the latest activities, participation in events, and achievements accomplished throughout the duration of the project. According to Pew Research Centre, 72% of adults use social media, with Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram, and LinkedIn being the most popular platforms (Social Media Fact Sheet, 2021). Additionally, social media is the top-ranked channel for connecting with target groups, and 57% of them will increase their attention and emotional investment if they feel connected to a brand (SproutSocial, 2018).

STA maintains the social media channels, announces the posts to all partners on a regular basis and tags relevant partners in the posts directly to draw their attention to the posts. Depending on the first analyses after 6 months, targeted ads may be activated on specific posts to target specific audience members during moments of consultation or co-creation.

2.2.3.1 LinkedIn

The LinkedIn profile has been created to raise awareness to the targeted audience (logistics operators and authorities), and additionally to gain publicity from the media and the public under the name "KEYSTONE EU" and using the logo in the profile picture. In the About section information about the project, the funding, and the main objectives of the project are provided as a quick overview for the visitor and a link for quick access to the official KEYSTONE website.

All posts related to the project should contain the hashtag #KEYSTONEproject to create a more united and easily recognizable identity of the project for the audience.

All consortium partners are welcome to share their activities related to KEYSTONE and use the hashtag mentioned above. Also, we highly recommend all partners repost and reshare the posts related to the project on their official accounts.

2.2.3.2 Twitter (X)

The X (formerly known as Twitter) KEYSTONE profile "@KEYSTONE_EU" was created in June 2023 as a tool to achieve fast, concise engagement with the targeted audience and public.

X reaches a significant number of policymakers and institutional actors and most importantly journalists and people working on the press media, which can enhance the communication and dissemination of the project. Additionally, one of KEYSTONE's communication strategies in the X social media platform will be more targeted and dynamic, identifying X channels that are related to the activities of the KEYSTONE project and will increase the audience.

It is highly recommended to all partners to use the hashtag #KEYSTONEEU in all posts related and add the official website of the project for further information as X has a limitation of 280 characters per post. A very helpful key is tagging relevant accounts in a tweet. For instance, when members of the consortium appear in a photo or an activity by adding a tag it is very likely they will reshare it and in this way, a broader audience will be reached.

2.2.4 Dissemination Materials Form

In order to follow and observe any kind of communication and dissemination action from all partners, a Google form was created and shared with all partners to report any communication and dissemination activity that has been completed. The form consists of 11 sections of mostly multiple-choice questions aiming to identify the owner/manager of the communication action that took place, the type of the action, and the targeted audience (total number of people reached). This tool will be used by all members of the consortium after completing an activity and has been already introduced early on during the Kick-Off Meeting of the project in Brussels during the first month of the project.

2.3 Consortium Digital Communication Tools

Apart from the dedicated KEYSTONE communication tools, and in order to achieve the maximum potential outreach, the following table was created to demonstrate the potential outreach of each consortium partner. The vast majority of consortium partners have an established and highly relevant presence on the social networks, which may also be utilized to spread project communications. Beyond this, the need to promote the project's activities through the personal accounts of the team members involved in KEYSTONE's activities was highlighted as well, which can prove in some cases to be a more powerful tool than a company page on social media, as the click-through rates of such posts tend to be significantly higher. Additionally, the figures show us that there is a very high audience that can be reached through X & LinkedIn, specifically by accumulating the total follower's number on LinkedIn, 665,492 people, and for X 83,061. In total, the consortium can reach 748,553 people by creating awareness on their social media accounts. Below the table presents the figures by partner. The data were issued on 01 September 2023, by the time of the submission of the paper the data might be changed accordingly. As demonstrated in the table below, the consortium has no existing outreach on Facebook, and not many key stakeholders or target audience members have been identified on this social network which is why no resources are dedicated to maintaining a dedicated page on Facebook.

Table 4 - Consortium online communication tools

Organisation	X		LinkedIn		Facebook	
	Existent?	Followers	Existent?	Followers	Existent?	Followers
UNIMORE	✓	6,277	✓	85,901		-
TTS Italia	✓	1,278	✓	2,585	✓	-
TBridge (BV Tech)	✓	264	✓	15,199		-
RINA	✓	2,713	✓	284,358		-
Etelätär Innovation	✓	307	✓	422		-
Smart Transportation Alliance	✓	1,928	✓	299		-
Technical University of Madrid	✓	48,100	✓	255,386		-
Aethon Engineering	✓	70	✓	1,597	✓	262
Gruber Logistics	✓	196	✓	18,872	✓	6,947
CIM		-		-	✓	180
Cefriel	✓	14,200	✓	10,834		-
Corte		-		-		-
Spanish Road Association (AEC)	✓	7,882	✓	4,840	✓	1
ICOOR	✓	110	✓	398		-

2.4 KEYSTONE Printed Materials

Apart from the digital communication channels created to promote the project's actions, several offline communication activities need to be designed, created, printed and shared to make the target audience aware of the project's strategies and aims. The scope of the offline materials is to attract people's attention to KEYSTONE's objectives and ensure that the concept and activities are communicated in an efficient way to the potential target group audience and stakeholders and to the public. The overall aim of the offline communication activities is to raise awareness for KEYSTONE at the national and European levels. Apart from the materials described in the sub-chapters below, an effort should be made to also produce banners, stickers or other materials that can be used during the piloting stage of the web app and to mark check-points or trucks who are users of the system to facilitate the piloting. This "branding" can also be carried over after the end of the project for replication activities, spreading the word amongst operators and authorities on-site.

2.4.1 Roll-ups

Over the duration of KEYSTONE, two roll-ups will be created at regular intervals to enhance the project's objectives. Roll-ups represent useful communication material to be used in different events, workshops, or any other event open to the public with a higher participation level. In year 1, two different roll-ups will be created – one has already been presented to the partners at the Kick-Off Meeting in Brussels in month 1 of the project (June 2023), and a second one will be distributed to the project partners at the second physical meeting of the Steering Committee (SC) in Novara, Italy in month 6 of the project (November 2023).

While the first roll-up had a very temporary design, with the key information of the project to mark the meeting room of the Kick-Off Meeting, it was designed in a way that it can be re-used for the entirety of the project, adding visual diversity to booths or events by using more than one roll-up design.

The second edition contains more detailed information and also highlights the main outcomes and gains for the industry and authorities to draw their attention. A copy of this roll-up is shared with each partner and it can be used during the entire project duration.

2.4.2 Posters

During the duration of the project, two different types of posters will be designed and distributed, one in year 1, along with the roll-up in Project Month 6 and the other one in year 2. The first poster will have a versatile design, which will be aligned with the visual identity of the overall project. The concept of this first poster is to serve not only as an introduction to the project, but also to provide the consortium partners with a template that they can adapt to local or internal contexts. This way, the format of the poster can also be used to promote or inform about events, focus discussion groups or it can be used to share handy one-page factsheets beyond the consortium for example in form of visual materials for social media or presentations. The purpose of the second poster will be to summarise final or preliminary results and findings and include calls to action for replication or follower activities.

2.4.3 Brochures

Brochures are a key element for the communication and dissemination plan of the project and the general public, since they can convey and carry information beyond a presentation, conversation or social media post and remain in the possession of the target audience member. The brochures will be distributed at events, consortium partners offices and local activities as a visual document to provide more detailed information about the project and its scope, objectives, activities, and latest news with relevant target audiences and stakeholders and provide readers will all of the key links and resources they need.

The layout and contents of the brochure have been co-created in collaboration with the consortium partners at the physical SC meeting in November 2023 (M6). The brochures will be created in year 2, where the participation in events will be higher and additionally, more activities and outcomes of year 1 can be presented and more visual materials such as pictures and infographics can be included.

2.5 KEYSTONE Publications

To support the dissemination strategy towards national, regional, and European stakeholders, academia, research centres, enforcement authorities, press and media, and related R&D initiatives a total of ten papers will be produced. The papers will be produced from year 2 of the project and will contain the most interesting inputs and goals accomplished so far. The papers are an active academic discussion concerning the development and conceptualization of a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport system for data exchange. Furthermore, publications pave the way for further in-depth research in data exchange. All publications will be rendered free for Open Access (OA), so that the results of KEYSTONE remain easily findable.

Within the first year of the project, project coordinator UNIMORE has already used the opportunity to present a full conference paper for the 2024 edition of the Transport Research Arena, where the project will also be present at a shared booth stand.

2.5.1 Conference Papers

Conference reports will provide the reader with an overview of the conference, explaining the main idea and a historical record of the event. Additionally, will provide information about the main idea that was discussed and all other activities that might have taken place. During year one no conference papers will be published, and in year 2 and 3, three conference papers in each year, six in total.

2.5.2 Journal Papers

Journal papers are mainly academic papers published and containing relevant results or reviewing existing results on the topic. During year 1, there will not be any publication of journals, however in years 2 and 3, journals will be submitted, two in each project year as by year two the project will have progressed more. Journals will help to promote KEYSTONE to increase its impact on the scientific community. Alternative, more cost-effective ways to achieve publications are used as a main avenue to achieve this outreach, namely the Open Research Europe Platform (which offers a peer-review free of charge) or Conference Papers, for which it is possible to opt into a formal journal publication and peer-review.

Since the publication in journals via traditional routes are more cost- and time intensive, their publication may only be achieved following the end of the KEYSTONE project and although their impact should be taken into account, it has to be anticipated that their publication date follows the final reporting on the communication & dissemination reporting in M36 of the project. In this case, the topic and submission date of the publication is documented and the project partners vouch to share the news of the publication eventually on their social media channels and websites following the end of the EU-funded period.

2.6 KEYSTONE Events

Events are a profound instrument in disseminating information and engaging with the partners of the consortium, the targeted audience, stakeholders, and the general audience. Since the opinions, input and co-creation of the end users are of crucial importance not only for the successful implementation of the project as a whole but in particular to the development of its main KERs, and since many specialised events and platforms already exist in the industry today, events hold a high importance for the KEYSTONE consortium. The consortium partners shall do their utmost to be able to present KEYSTONE and its objectives in a dedicated presentation, agora session or site-meeting whenever they plan to attend a conference related to the project, whether it be on local, national or European level. In the presentation template, which will be presented in sub-chapter 3.4, an invitation to register to the newsletter has been integrated by design to ensure a high visibility of this tool, and subsequently the registration of contacts for co-creation and consultation activities.

2.6.1 Project Events

Three annual project events will be held during the duration of the project. The events aim to promote and disseminate the KEYSTONE objectives, results, and overall achievements and to engage all relevant targeted audiences to the activities of the project.

Additionally, participation in events is a great opportunity for all consortium partners to get together and present the progress made so far, and exchange ideas and feedback.

The Consortium Meeting 1 will take place on 28-29 November in Novara (Italy), where all partners will have the opportunity to engage and exchange opinions about the project and the outcomes.

2.6.2 External Events

During the three years of the duration of the project, a large number of external events will take place, such as conferences, seminars, workshops, and meetings at a national or international level. All consortium partners should decide what they will communicate and also the audience they will address. Since all partners have reserved a travel budget to attend external events, each one has identified events of high relevance and interest for them. Although the first year of the project has only just reached its half-time, four events have already been identified, which will be attended by one or more KEYSTONE consortium partners and involve a presentation on-site:

- Supply Chain & Logistics Athens, 30 September – 02 October 2023, Athens (Greece) by Aethon Engineering;
- 2023 STA Annual Conference & Innovation Awards, 26 October 2023, Milan (Italy) by STA;
- NAPCORE Mobility Data, (National Access Point Coordination Organization for Europe), 07-09 November 2023, Budapest (Hungary) by Aethon Engineering;
- TRA (Transport Research Arena), 15-18 April 2024, Dublin (Ireland) by UNIMORE and STA.

For the next years of the project, a list of targeted events has already been identified and the organisers have been contacted and/or are informed of the KEYSTONE project to involve the consortium in the programme agenda early on to ensure a high visibility of the project at the events. The full list can be found in Table 5 below. Further events may be added or certain events might be removed from the list, depending on the perceived value for money of attending the events in person by the consortium partners. To ensure high visibility, attendance of any event should always be linked to an opportunity to present KEYSTONE to a wide audience – whether it be a presentation, a keynote speech, an agora session, a workshop, a site-meeting, a poster, a booth, a pitch or similar.

Table 5 - Targeted future external events

Name	Location	Date
ROADPOL Safety Days	EU-Wide	16-22 September 2023
PIARC World Road Congress	Prague, Czech Republic	02-06 October 2023
Intermodal Europe 2023	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	10-12 October 2023
Digital Logistics Conference 2023	Online	11-12 October 2023
CEN Standards + Innovation Awards 2023	Brussels, Belgium & Online	26 October 2023
7th Annual European Supply Chain Management Strategies Summit	Munich, Germany	07-08 November 2023
RTR Conference	Brussels, Belgium	05-07 February 2024
Semaine de l'Innovation du Transport et de la Logistique (SITL)	Paris, France	19-21 March 2024
LogiMAT	Stuttgart, Germany	19-21 March 2024
SIL 2023	Barcelona, Spain	05-07 June 2024
Transport Logistic	Munich, Germany	02-05 June 2025
TRA 2026	???	???

3. KEYSTONE Visual Identity Handbook

A clear visual identity is a cornerstone of a successful communications and dissemination strategy as the presentation of a unique and consistent image makes the project more recognizable by the wider public and within the industry. A visual identity handbook consists of all visual and stylised elements that create a holistic image of the project, a branding. Despite the term “brand” is mostly associated to commercial companies, research and development activities and funded projects can greatly profit from the principles of a branding to enhance their attractiveness and attract more attention by all of their audiences. It is important to strike a fine balance between modern design and serious and professional values the project wants to convey.

KEYSTONE seeks in conveying a set of clear associations with its visual identity, namely reliability, research, technology and digital tools. How these are integrated into the different elements of the project is described below. The key visual elements of the project are presented and detailed, which serve the consortium partners in correctly applying the same visual identity across countries, work packages, topics, sectors and languages.

Apart from the project’s visual identity, any project document, presentation, result, database, publication or else result need to carry three distinct disclaimers, which need to be implemented and respected by all partners and which have been implemented by design into all templates and the website to comply with Horizon Europe and the Grant Agreement funding conditions:

1. “Funded by the European Union” disclaimer, which consists of a simple image, containing the EU flag and the text, and which has been made available all types of formats and colour combinations to the partners in the common project repository (see also the bottom left corner of this deliverable);
2. A disclaimer to differentiate the contents of any result from the European Union and CINEA: “Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.” needs to be included to ensure that the results are linked to the author, and not the funding body (see also the third page of this deliverable).
3. A short copyright disclaimer, associating the contents to the KEYSTONE consortium for IPR protection: “Copyright 2023-2026 © KEYSTONE consortium.” (see also bottom of each page of this deliverable).

3.1 Logo

The logo is a key part of creating a consistent image to ensure wide useability throughout the project for both online and offline communication materials and meanwhile to raise awareness on the targeted group. The logo is the signature of the KEYSTONE project that may be added to all activities of the project to make the project more recognizable and understandable. The KEYSTONE logo was created in co-creation with the consortium partners and can be found in Figure 3 provided below in different sizes and formats to fit in different backgrounds, the main logo is the very first on the top left.

Apart from a central logo, favicons and alternative versions are provided to the consortium for different uses. The logo is available in all versions and ultra-high resolution to all partners in the common sharepoint and needs to be included in any communication or dissemination of the project in a prominent way. Depending on the material, it may make sense to apply a favicon (only the logotype) or the entire logo, which may be decided on a case-to-case basis. Where possible, the main logo including the title of the project should be applied.

The symbol of the logo consists of three crossing roads, as the project is about international cross- border compliance of road logistics and freight. An arrow with an upward direction is depicted, representing the innovation and the upscaling of digitisation. Additionally, the crossed roads represent the different organizations in the consortium as there are 15 partners from 6 countries across the continent, who join their forces for the KEYSTONE project.

Each of the colours stands for one of the key principles of KEYSTONE:

1. Safety and security (blue);
2. Data and compliance (yellow);
3. Digitization, automatization and technology (orange);
4. Logistics and reliability (dark blue).

Figure 3 - KEYSTONE logos & favicons

3.2 Font

The chosen font for KEYSTONE is Arial. This font is used for any kind of written deliverable in the KEYSTONE project as it is a clean, contemporary font with a simple and standard style, that functions well for body texts. Apart from its versatility, it is also a convenience font, since it is detected easily by accessibility readers for accessibility requirements, provides a high contrast and is readily available on any device, including even smartphones and mobile devices. This provides two advantages: on the one hand Arial will always be able to be displayed on the devices and on the other hand no additional fonts need to be installed in order to design or draft deliverables or other materials.

Arial
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Arial Bold Italic

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3.3 Color Palette

KEYSTONE has a colour palette that is used repeatedly in all materials, deliverables, and presentations related to the project, it can be found in Figure 4 below. The project aims to create digital fast-track compliance and security channels for road transport drivers and logistics. It seeks cooperation between logistic operators, authorities, and drivers over a pre-defined European corridor (Milan-Switzerland-Germany-Belgium). The selection of the colour palette of the logo was based on the general theory of emotional colour guides:

- The blue-shaded colours represent trust, protection, stability, and confidence;
- The orange colour is associated with confidence, technology and data;
- The yellow colour represents optimism, happiness and a positive change.

Figure 4 - KEYSTONE project colour palette & HEX codes

3.4 PowerPoint Template

The PowerPoint template is a custom-made template designed for the use of the consortium partners while presenting anything related to the KEYSTONE project at events, conferences, agora centres, webinars, or during any internal meeting between consortium partners in a consistent way. The custom-made slides featured below present some of the presentation slides, to provide the reader an idea of the design of the templates. The full version of the PowerPoint presentation template can be found in ANNEX II - KEYSTONE Presentation Template.

It is compulsory for all consortium partners to use only the project presentation template for official dissemination activities of the project and refrain from using their own organisation’s presentation templates. Great attention has been paid to comply with the accessibility requirements of public authorities (one of the KEYSTONE target groups), the effective implementation of the visual identity, and the provision of a wide range of graphics, images, and presentation options to present the information in an engaging and innovative way. The template seeks in encouraging the consortium partners to tell a story with each presentation, and adapt their phrasing and tone to the requirements of their audience.

Figure 5 - KEYSTONE presentation template example

3.5 Written Report Template

All the written reports in the KEYSTONE project follow the same formatting to create a more familiar look of the project and recognition of all partners and to ensure that all deliverables and documents adhere strictly to the funding rules of the Horizon Europe programme and the Grant Agreement alike. The current document follows the same template. In the following figures, the word template for KEYSTONE is introduced. Although ANNEX III – KEYSTONE Written Report Template contains the full template, the following figures present the most important layout details.

In the same way than for the presentation template, a special effort has been made to ensure a high contrast and accessibility of the template to ensure full accessibility and functionality to adapt the document to any use from the documentation of complex technical information to the presentation of simple agendas and meeting minutes.

In both the case of the templates for presentation and written reports, the entire consortium was consulted on every step of the way and all partners had the opportunity to stress-test the templates to ensure their full functionality for their individual purposes.

Figure 6 - KEYSTONE written report template

4. Yearly Editorials

An editorial plan has been created to plan precisely the communication and dissemination responsibilities to the members of the consortium throughout the duration of the project. The editorial calendar presents the activities on a monthly basis, as an attempt to plan all the communication & dissemination activities as described by the KPIs and to engage all partners to the communication strategy of KEYSTONE. In this way, the success of the communication plan will be highly successful, and all partners will contribute to it.

Below the editorial calendar is presented and in the previous sections, all the activities are explained in detail (regularity, additional information). During the WP6 meetings, a more detailed version of the editorial plan (on a weekly rather than monthly level) is discussed and responsibilities and tasks are distributed between partners.

	2023									2024									2025									2026									
	M 1	M 2	M 3	M 4	M 5	M 6	M 7	M 8	M 9	M 10	M 11	M 12	M 13	M 14	M 15	M 16	M 17	M 18	M 19	M 20	M 21	M 22	M 23	M 24	M 25	M 26	M 27	M 28	M 29	M 30	M 31	M 32	M 33	M 34	M 35	M 36	
Newsletter																																					
Social Media Posts- Twitter			2 posts monthly																																		
Social Media Posts- LinkedIn																																					
Video clips																																					
Roll-ups																																					
Posters																																					
Brochures																																					
Conference Papers																																					
Journal Papers																																					
Project Events																																					
Attendance to external events																																					
Website	1 piece of news monthly																																				

5. Conclusions

The KEYSTONE communication and dissemination plan is an essential tool for the overall implementation of the project and the successful and targeted dissemination of project results. The Work Package (WP) 6 – Communication, Dissemination, Replicability and Exploitation, Deliverable D6.3 presents the communication and dissemination activities that should be carried out by all partners throughout the duration of the project.

The main objective of the deliverable is to highlight the methods and timing of the upcoming activities to engage the targeted audience and raise awareness among the public so that the activities of the project become well-known at a European level. Furthermore, it serves in introducing partners inside and outside of the consortium to the dissemination channels and tools and how they should be used to avoid misalignment of communications.

Two more editions of the deliverable will be published as part of the (WP) 6 - D6.4 Communication and Dissemination Plan Update D6.4 in Project Month 18, containing a more detailed description of the work plan for the Communication & Dissemination Strategy, any changes that might occur concerning the visual identity throughout the project, any other updates might be included in the report and the Final Communication and Dissemination Report D6.5 in Project Month 36, that shall include a final overview of all the activities that took place throughout the project. Both of these deliverables also serve as a good moment to report on the achieved KPIs of both the project tools and analysing the individual contributions by project partners.

ANNEX I - Website Overview

ANNEX II - KEYSTONE Presentation Template

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KEYSTONE

Thank you!

[Presenter Name]
[Affiliation]
[email address]

www.keystone-project.com

ANNEX III – KEYSTONE Written Report Template

Disclaimer

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 This deliverable is a draft document subject to revision until formal approval by the European Commission.
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Deliverable details

Horizon Europe GA no.	Project acronym	Project title
101103740	KEYSTONE	Knowledgeable comprehensive and fully integrated smart solution for resilient, sustainable and optimized transport operations

Deliverable	Title	Work package
DX.X	XXX	WFX

Contractual delivery date	Project month	Actual delivery date	Delivery type	Dissemination level
DD MONTH YY	PM X	DD MONTH YY	R/DEM	PU/SEN

Author(s)	Organization
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 KEYSTONE

Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101103740

Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
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Document history

Version	Date	Author	Affiliation	Summary
V0.1	DD MONTH YEAR	John Doe	Partner	ToC & Executive Summary
V0.2	DD MONTH YEAR	John Doe	Partner	
V0.3	DD MONTH YEAR	John Doe	Partner	
V1.0	DD MONTH YEAR	John Doe	Partner	Final review & conversion to PDF format

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Deliverable D [X.X]
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 KEYSTONE

Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No 101103740

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Deliverable D [X.X]
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1. Executive Summary

Each Deliverable should contain an executive summary, which summarizes on 1 page the purpose and applied methodology of the following work. The reader should be able to identify the different parts of the report and chose those parts which are of interest to them, while understanding the overall scope of the report.

For the body of text, the text style 'Text Body' is used, of Arial, 11pt, bloc justified with 12pt after the paragraph and 1.1 spacing between paragraph lines.

2. Heading 1

2.1 Heading 2

2.1.1 Heading 3

2.1.1.1 Heading 4

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Figure 1. Caption

Table 1. Title

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3. Conclusions

Similarly to the Executive Summary, each document also needs to contain a conclusions section, which summarizes the findings of the Deliverable on 1-3 pages and provides the reader with a comprehensive outlook concerning it's impact on the following project activities.

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EXAMPLE AUTO ADAPTING LANDSCAPE PAGE

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